

Individualism in the Novels of Chetan Bhagat

Professor Tulshikatti D. C.

Head of the Department, Department of English, Chandrabai-Shantappa Shendure College, Hupari Dist.
Kolhapur 416203 Maharashtra, India

Corresponding author E-mail: tulshikattidc48@gmail.com

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Chetan Bhagat undoubtedly a gifted writer in handling the themes and major issues that are related to the youth and their concerns in particular. As mentioned earlier, it is no exaggeration to call him an exclusive and excellent author in the sight of the youth. He always tries to the extent possible to give voices to the unheard feelings, emotions, opinions, and inner thought of the youth in each of his novels. A careful study of Chetan Bhagat's novels by a reader can sense the major themes – liberty, concern and problems of youth and individualism in all his writings.

In his debut novel, *Five Point Someone*, the three major characters – Hari, Alok and Ryan who always strive for liberty and individualism to the maximum extent possible in their lives. They least bothered about the education system which is existed at IIT Delhi. Unlike other students they never kept quiet in raising their voices and fight bravely against the very old and meaningless rules that are made by the old educationists whose knowledge was confined and limited to some extent. In the guise of these three said characters; Chetan reveals the horrible education system at IIT Delhi in an able and effective manner. He makes a dare attempt in criticizing meaningless education system at IIT Delhi where the students are compelled to concentrate on their examinations by mugging up the subjects instead of giving place to knowledge a top priority. The educationists bother least about the creativity which is viewed as an important skill in the sight of employers in all the reputed companies at present. All the three protagonists raise their voices against of these age-old educationists and shirking their classes without caring them and above all giving much weightage to the urgent required qualities by the present corporate world such as innovation, creativity, practical knowledge and self-respect. They do not worry much about the comments made by their teacher and other students when they underperform in the exams; instead, they feel proud for being freethinkers and icons of liberty and individualism. In the entire novel Chetan not only depicts the problems and issues of the young students but also expresses his marvelous thoughts how best these young minds can be dealt in a highly effective way.

In 'One Night @ the call center' all the six characters have some unwanted desires and they all want to fulfill the unwanted desires and for that they have to undergone the traumatic problems and after the final call from the God all the problems of all the characters are solved. They set their goals and they promise to

follow the goals according to their desires and finally all the characters attain the peace and their stress is decrease to some level. Thus, the writer has succeeded in presenting the problems of today's era in a very refectory manner. 'The Three Mistakes of My Life' is a remarkable hat trick by Chetan Bhagat after his debut 'Five Point Someone' and second novel 'One Night @ the call center'. Bhagat seems to continue the same passionate zeal in presenting hopes and aspiration as well as failure and frustration of his generation in remarkable fashion. The novel ironically unfolds some of the bitter truths of human life which is now more influenced by passion rather than emotion and ambition. Chetan Bhagat is more vibrant in this novel because of his growing maturity and sharpening sensibility. 'The Three mistakes of My Life' studies the passionate ambition of three growing boys Govind Patel, Ishaan and Omi. The narrator of this sensational story is Govind himself. Govind is more obsessed have occupied with different life- style. Ishaan has passion of cricket while Omi more concerned with religion because of his parents' attachment with city temple. So, business, cricket and religion seem to govern the life of these growing people. Bhagat studies the characters of these three with ironic detachment because he never takes the sides of any one. The novel also contains some real incidents like- earthquake on the Republic Day, The test match between India and Australia at Eden Garden in which India wins marginally. These portrayals give a unique kind of realistic touch to the novel. So, Bhagat blends the sociopolitical motive of Anand with the psychological realism of Narayan in this novel with his brilliant way of storytelling.

The Three Mistakes of My Life

It is Bhagat's third book, about cricket, religious politics and rebellious love. About how three friends get caught in a tangle to earn some money and fame, and how they sort it out. The book was published in May 2008 and had an initial print –run of 200,000 copies. The novel follows the story of three friends and is based in the city of Ahmadabad in western India where the author had begun his independent life and so this city is quite close to his heart. Farhan Akhtar's Excel Entertainment has bought the rights for making a movie based on this, and it will be directed by Abhishek Kapoor of 'ROCK ON!' fame.

The book has fiction: - sentiment, romance, social message, business, life, relations, religion and of course cricket. It's the story about three friends Omi, Govind and Ish who are struggling to decide their goal. The story is presented through Govind's eye; he is a brilliant student of mathematics. He has an aptitude and penchant for business and it's his three mistakes of life that are presented along. Govind is a true Gujarati, interested in coming up on his own in life through business. Ishaan or Ish- a failure in studies but a great cricketer (obviously great in the local school team), has a passion in playing, teaching and watching cricket. Omi comes from a family of priests with no inclination of becoming a priest and just moves along with his two friends.

The journey of these simple people in life, how their lives get affected by the worst disasters in Gujarat's history is portrayed in a simple yet efficient way by Chetan Bhagat. This book also teaches you how your dreams crash into pieces by unexpected events but how with the support from people around, you gets back on track, focus and rebuild your dreams.

Vidya, Ishaan's sister, a teenager with her eyes on Govind, represents typically homely Indian girls trying to lose their virginity and so-called boys feeling shy and guilty after having sex with them.... as Neha in 'Five Point Someone' and here Vidya in this novel. Ali, a gifted batsman and son of a local Muslim politician, plays a prominent role in the story. It's the story of how Govind, Ishaan and Omi come up with a sports store in their area and how they achieve success in it by clubbing it with Math's tuitions and cricket coaching classes. The writer has thrown in the angle of Ali a gifted batsman who is in need of coaching and as Ishaan is an avid cricket player whose passion lies in playing, teaching and watching cricket, comes in as Ali's savior because he does not want a brilliant talent to be wasted. Then there is a love angle of Vidya and Govind thrown in. And to top it all Chetan Bhagat has placed the novel in the era when Ahmadabad suffered with a nightmare of an earthquake and riots. The book traces the lives of these characters and their trials and tribulations.

This novel especially comes at a time when people only want to come up with excuses to show or feel how different they are rather than see the common aspects and bring oneness which can keep us together and achieve our common goal of growth, peace and prosperity. The language is simple, it connects well with the youth of India and the narration has improved as compared to the earlier novels. Chetan Bhagat has again proved that to be best novelist you don't need fabulous vocabulary or you don't need awesome critics review, all you need is a thread to connect to the plain minds of people. Truly this novel teaches you- life will have many setbacks. People close to you will hurt you, but you don't break it off, you don't hurt them more. You try to heal it. It is a lesson not only you, but our country needs to learn.

Ashwani Rana 71 The story involves some of the major headlines of early 2000 like the Gujarat earthquake, India- Australia test series, the 9/11 WTC attack and not to forget the Godhra train mishap. Apart from cricket, business and religion it also has the mesmerizing love story between Govind and Vidya the story is good, since the events are from recent past and it's easy to connect with it. It can be completed in one sitting. But there are not many surprises as it has not gone away from Bhagat's typical style of writing. It is less on humor content as well. Chetan has been very clever by stating '3 mistakes' and you keep flipping the pages for knowing the other two mistakes as the first mistake you will come to know quite soon. It is a book with nice ingredients of real events and fiction perfectly cooked for a delicious dish. No mistake in giving it a read.

2 States: The Story of My Marriage is the fourth novel of Chetan Bhagat. The novel is about an IIMA couple's struggle to marry over the cultural differences. It's a story of an inter-state marriage in India; a Love story of a Punjabi boy Krish, and a Tamil Brahmin girl Ananya and marriage of parathas and idlis, paneer and coconut. Krish and Ananya, the main protagonists, are lovers but contrary to the usual practice they do not elope. They, instead, choose to convince their parents to approve of their tying the nuptial knot.

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